

Studies in the Synthesis of Furocoumarins: Part XVIII.* Synthesis of 2-Methyl-9-oxo-9H-furo (2, 3-c) benzopyran Derivatives

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2-Methyl-9-oxo-9H-furo(2,3-c)benzopyran is synthesised from 3-hydroxycoumarin by allylation, Claisen migration, acetylation, bromination and cyclisation with alcoholic potassium hydroxide. 7-Methoxy-2-methyl-9-oxo-9H-2,3-dihydrofuro(2,3-c)benzopyran and 6-bromo-2-methyl-9-oxo-9H-2,3-dihydrofuro(2,3-c)benzopyran are also synthesised but attempts to dehydrogenate these with palladised charcoal met with failure.

IN continuation of our earlier work on furocoumarins derived from 3-hydroxycoumarin¹, we report here the synthesis of a few more furocoumarins of this type from 3-hydroxycoumarin derivatives.

2-Methyl-9-oxo-9H-furo (2,3-c) benzopyran¹ (IIIa) was also prepared according to the method developed by Kaufmann².

3-Hydroxycoumarin (Ia) on allylation with allyl bromide and potassium carbonate in refluxing acetone, afforded the 3-allyloxy derivative (Ib) which on Claisen rearrangement gave 4-allyl-3-hydroxycoumarin (Ic). This on acetylation with acetic anhydride and fused sodium acetate, gave 4-allyl-3-acetoxycoumarin (Ij), which on bromination with bromine in acetic acid afforded 4-(2',3'-dibromopropyl)-3-acetoxycoumarin (Ik). (Ik) when refluxed with alcoholic potassium hydroxide furnished 2-methyl-9-oxo-9H-furo(2,3-c)benzopyran (IIIa).

8-Methoxy-3-hydroxycoumarin³ (Id) on allylation followed by Claisen rearrangement by refluxing with dimethyl aniline in an atmosphere of nitrogen gave 8-methoxy-4-allyl-3-hydroxycoumarin (If). The structure (If) was also supported by its n.m.r. spectrum, which showed the following signals.

Shift (δ) ppm.	Signals	Assignments
3.6	Doublet	2H, = CH-CH ₂ group
4.0	Singlet	3H, -OCH ₃ group at position 8
5.2	Doublet	2H, = CH ₂ group
5.8	Multiplet	1H, -CH group
6.4	Singlet	1H, -OH group
7.2	Multiplet	3H, aromatic protons

8-Methoxy-3-allyloxy coumarin (Ie) when heated at 180°C for 30 min, afforded a mixture of two compounds, as indicated by TLC. The separation of the mixture was carried out by fractional crystallisation. The product which was soluble in alcohol and developed green colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride

was identical with (If) in all respects. The compound which was insoluble in alcohol and did not develop any colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride was assigned 7-methoxy-2-methyl-9-oxo-9H-2,3-dihydrofuro(2,3-c)benzopyran (IIa) structure. This was also supported by n.m.r. spectrum of the compound which showed the following signals.

Shift (δ) ppm.	Signals	Assignments
2.1	Doublet	3H, -CH ₃ group at position 2
3.2	Multiplet	2H, -CH ₂ group at position 3
3.9	Singlet	3H, -OCH ₃ group at position 7
5.2	Multiplet	1H, -proton at position 2
7.1	Multiplet	3H, -aromatic protons.

The compound (IIa) was also obtained, when 8-methoxy-4-allyl-3-hydroxycoumarin (If) was cyclised by heating at 200°C for 1 hr. The mixed m.p. with the compound prepared as above was not depressed.

Attempts to cyclise 8-methoxy-4-allyl-3-hydroxycoumarin (If) to (IIa) with other methods like triturating with sulphuric acid, heating with o-phosphoric acid, polyphosphoric acid and with hydrobromic acid in acetic acid or pyridine hydrochloride was found to be unsuccessful.

7-Methoxy-2-methyl-9-oxo-9H-2,3-dihydrofuro(2,3-c)benzopyran (IIa) could not be dehydrogenated with palladised charcoal, the original compound was recovered unchanged.

Synthesis of 7-methoxy-2-methyl-9-oxo-9H-furo(2,3-c)benzopyran (IIIb) by a different route² was also attempted. 8-Methoxy-4-allyl-3-hydroxycoumarin (If) on acetylation followed by bromination gave 8-methoxy-4-(2', 3'-dibromopropyl)-3-acetoxycoumarin (Im). This when refluxed with alcoholic potassium hydroxide or sodium and absolute alcohol, gave a pasty product from which no pure 7-methoxy-2-methyl-9-oxo-9H-furo(2,3-c)benzopyran (IIIb) could be isolated.

Similarly 6-bromo-3-hydroxycoumarin⁴ (Ig) was converted to 5-bromo-2-methyl-9-oxo-9H-2,3-dihydrofuro(2,3-c)benzopyran (IIb). Attempts to dehydrogenate (IIb) to 5-bromo-2-methyl-9-oxo-9H-furo(2,3-c)

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benzopyran (IIIc) with palladised charcoal were, however, unsuccessful.

- (a) $R = R_1 = R_2 = R_3 = H$
 (b) $R = -CH_2-CH = CH_2$; $R_1 = R_2 = R_3 = H$
 (c) $R_1 = -CH_2-CH = CH_2$; $R = R_2 = R_3 = H$
 (d) $R = R_1 = R_2 = H$; $R_3 = -OCH_3$
 (e) $R = -CH_2-CH = CH_2$; $R_1 = R_2 = H$; $R_3 = -OCH_3$
 (f) $R_1 = -CH_2 = CH-CH_2$; $R = R_2 = H <$; $R_3 = -OCH_3$
 (g) $R = R_1 = R_3 = H$; $R_2 = Br$
 (h) $R = -CH_2-CH = CH_2 <$; $R_1 = R_2 = H$; $R_3 = Br$
 (i) $R_1 = -CH_2-CH = CH_2$; $R = R_2 = H$; $R_3 = Br$
 (j) $R = -COCH_3 <$; $R_1 = -CH_2-CH = CH_2 <$; $R_2 = R_3 = H$
 (k) $R = -COCH_3$; $R_1 = -CH_2-CHBr-CH_2Br$; $R_2 = R_3 = H$
 (l) $R = -COCH_3$; $R_1 = -CH_2-CH = CH_2$; $R_2 = H$; $R_3 = -OCH_3$
 (m) $R = -COCH_3$; $R_1 = -CH_2-CHBr-CH_2Br$; $R_2 = H$; $R_3 = -OCH_3$

- (a) $R = H$; $R_1 = -OCH_3$
 (b) $R = Br$; $R_1 = H$

- (a) $R = R_1 = H$
 (b) $R = H$; $R_1 = -OCH_3$
 (c) $R = Br$; $R_1 = H$

Experimental

N.M.R. Spectra were recorded on varian A-60 spectrophotometer using TMS as internal standard.

3-Allyloxycoumarin (Ib): 3-Hydroxycoumarin (3.5 g), allylbromide (2.5 ml) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (5 g) in dry acetone (100 ml) was refluxed in a water bath for 10 hr. The product which obtained on evaporation of acetone was treated with water and filtered. A benzene solution of the dried product was run over a short column of alumina and the compound was eluted with benzene. Evaporation of the solvent left a residue which crystallised

from benzene, m.p. 98°C. Yield 3 g. It did not develop green colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride solution. (Found: C, 71.13; H, 4.53; calc. for $C_{12}H_{10}O_3$: C, 71.28; H, 4.95%).

4-Allyl-3-hydroxycoumarin (Ic): 3-Allyloxycoumarin (3 g) was refluxed with dimethyl aniline (8 ml) under nitrogen atmosphere for 3 hr. The reaction mixture was poured into conc. ice cold hydrochloric acid (25 ml) and was left overnight. The solid which separated was filtered, washed with water and dried. A benzene solution of the dried compound was run over a short column of alumina and the compound was eluted with benzene. It crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 149°C. Yield 2 g. It developed green colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride solution which is the characteristic of 3-hydroxycoumarin derivatives. (Found: C, 70.86; H, 4.63; calc. for $C_{12}H_{10}O_3$: C, 71.28; H, 4.95%).

4-Allyl-3-acetoxycoumarin (Ij): A mixture of 4-allyl-3-hydroxycoumarin (1 g) and acetic anhydride (5 ml) containing a few crystals of freshly fused sodium acetate was heated under reflux for 5 hr. Excess of acetic anhydride was decomposed on stirring with water containing crushed ice. The separated product was collected by filtration and dried. The compound was purified by passing it in benzene over alumina as before. The product crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 122°C. Yield 0.9 g. It did not develop any colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride solution. (Found: C, 68.79; H, 4.83; calc. for $C_{14}H_{12}O_4$: C, 68.85; H, 4.91%).

3-Acetoxy-4(2',3'-dibromopropyl)coumarin (Ik): A solution of bromine (1.6 g; 0.01M) in acetic acid (15 ml) was added dropwise to a well stirred solution of 4-allyl-3-acetoxycoumarin (2.4 g; 0.01M) in acetic acid (15 ml); during the period of 1 hr. After stirring for another 1 hr the solution was diluted with ice water and allowed to stand. The separated product was filtered, and washed with little alcohol. It crystallised from absolute alcohol, m.p. 162°C. Yield 2 g. (Found: Br, 40.0; calc. for $C_{14}H_{12}O_4Br_2$: Br, 39.60%).

2-Methyl-9-oxo-9H-furo(2,3-c)benzopyran (IIIa): A solution of 3-acetoxy-4(2',3'-dibromopropyl)coumarin (2 g) in ethanolic potassium hydroxide (2.5 g in 75 ml absolute alcohol) was heated under reflux for 2 hr. and then concentrated to one third of its volume. Water (50 ml) was then added and the solution was immediately acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid and was ether extracted. Evaporation of the ether left a pasty product which was washed with liquid ammonia (10 ml, 10%) and then with water. A benzene solution of the dried solid was run over a short column of alumina, and eluted with benzene. The product crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether mixture, mixed m.p. with the compound prepared as described earlier¹ did not depress. M.P. 159°C. Yield 0.2 g. (Found: C, 71.71; H, 4.0; calc. for $C_{12}H_{18}O_3$: C, 72.0; H, 4.0%).

8-Methoxy-3-allyloxycoumarin (Ie): A mixture of 8-methoxy-3-hydroxycoumarin³ (3 g) (Id) allylbromide (2.5 ml), anhydrous potassium carbonate (5 g) in dry acetone (100 ml) was refluxed in a water

bath for 8 hr. The reaction mixture was worked up as before. The product crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 112°C. Yield 2 g. It did not develop any colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride solution. (Found : C, 67.09; H, 4.97; calc. for $C_{13}H_{12}O_4$: C, 67.23; H, 5.17%).

8-Methoxy-4-allyl-3-hydroxycoumarin (If) : 8-Methoxy-3-allyloxy coumarin (2 g) and dimethylaniline (8 ml) was refluxed in the atmosphere of nitrogen for 1 hr. The reaction mixture was poured into hydrochloric acid (30 ml) in crushed ice and allowed to stand for 2 hr. The solid which separated was filtered, washed and dried. It crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 176°C. Yield 1.2 g. (Found : C, 66.88; H, 4.82; calc. for $C_{13}H_{12}O_3$: C, 67.23; H, 5.17%).

(If) was also obtained when 8-methoxy-3-allyloxy coumarin (0.8 g) was heated at 180°C for 20 min. The reaction product was refluxed in alcohol (5 ml) and filtered hot. The product which separated on concentrating alcohol was filtered and recrystallised from alcohol, m.p. 176°C. Mixed m.p. with the product prepared as above was not depressed. It gave characteristic green colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride.

7-Methoxy-2-methyl-9-oxo-9H-2,3-dihydrofuro (2,3-c) *benzopyran* (IIa) : 8-Methoxy-4-allyl-3-hydroxycoumarin (If) (0.8 g) was heated at 180°C for 30 min. The reaction product was refluxed with alcohol (10 ml) and filtered hot. The alcohol insoluble product was washed with little hot alcohol and crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 268°C. Yield 0.2 g. It did not develop any colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride. (Found : C, 66.83; H, 5.06; calc. for $C_{13}H_{12}O_3$: C, 67.23; H, 5.17%).

The same compound (IIa) was also obtained when 8-methoxy-4-allyl-3-hydroxycoumarin (If) was heated at 200°C for 1 hr. m.p. 268°C. Mixed m.p. with the above product was not depressed.

Attempts to cyclise 8-methoxy-4-allyl-3-hydroxycoumarin to (IIa) with other reagents like conc. sulphuric acid or orthophosphoric acid, polyphosphoric acid, with hydrobromic acid and acetic acid was found to be unsuccessful.

Attempted dehydrogenation of 7-methoxy-2-methyl-9-oxo-9H-2,3-dihydrofuro(2,3-c) *benzopyran* : A solution of 7-methoxy-2-methyl-9-oxo-9H-2,3-dihydrofuro(2,3-c)benzopyran (0.5 g) in diphenyl ether was refluxed with palladised charcoal (0.4 g; 5% or 10%) for 6 hr. The reaction mixture was filtered hot and the filtrate was allowed to cool. The separated product was filtered and crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 268°C. It was found to be original compound. Mixed m.p. with (IIa) did not depress.

8-Methoxy-4-allyl-3-acetoxycoumarin (II) : A mixture of 8-methoxy-3-hydroxycoumarin (2 g) and acetic anhydride (10 ml) containing a few crystals of fused sodium acetate was heated under reflux for 5 hr. The reaction mixture was poured into crushed ice and was worked out as usual. The product crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 135°C. Yield 1.8 g. It did not develop any colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride. (Found : C, 65.69; H, 5.22; calc. for $C_{15}H_{14}O_5$: C, 65.69; H, 5.10%).

8-Methoxy-4-(2',3'-dibromopropyl)-3-acetoxycoumarin (Im) : A solution of bromine (1.6 g; 0.01M) in acetic acid (15 ml) was added dropwise to a well stirred solution of 8-methoxy-4-allyl-3-acetoxycoumarin (2.6 g; 0.01M) in acetic acid (20 ml) during a period of 1 hr. The solution was poured into crushed ice and allowed to stand. The product which separated was filtered. A methanol solution of the dried product was run over a short column of alumina. Evaporation of the solvent left a residue, which crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 172°C. Yield 2.0 g. (Found : Br, 36.60; calc. for $C_{15}H_{14}O_5Br_2$: Br, 36.86%)

Attempted cyclisation of 8-methoxy-4-(2',3'-dibromopropyl)-3-acetoxycoumarin to (IIIb) : (i) 8-Methoxy-4-(2',3'-dibromopropyl)-3-acetoxycoumarin (2.1 g) was heated under reflux for 2 hr with a solution of potassium hydroxide (2.6 g) in absolute alcohol (75 ml). The reaction mixture was worked up as before; which afforded a pasty product from which no pure 7-methoxy-9-oxo-9H-furo(2,3-c)benzopyran (IIIb) could be isolated.

(ii) To a solution of sodium (0.5 g) in absolute alcohol (25 ml) was added 8-methoxy-4-(2',3'-dibromopropyl)-3-acetoxycoumarin (2 g) and was refluxed for 2 hr. After cooling the solution was poured into ice cold hydrochloric acid (25 ml). The insoluble pasty product was taken in chloroform. After washing the chloroform extract with water the dried chloroform extract was run over a short column of alumina. Evaporation of the solvent left a pasty mass from which no pure compound could be isolated.

6-Bromo-3-allyloxy coumarin (Ih) : A mixture of 6-bromo-3-hydroxy coumarin⁴ (Ig) (3 g), allyl bromide and freshly ignited potassium carbonate (10 g) in dry acetone (100 ml) was heated under reflux in a water bath for 6 hr. The reaction mixture was worked out as before. The product crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 142°C. Yield 2 g (Found : C, 51.01; H, 3.06; Br, 28.33; calc. for $C_{12}H_9O_3Br$: C, 51.24; H, 3.20; Br, 28.46%).

6-Bromo-4-allyl-3-hydroxycoumarin (Ii) : 6-Bromo-3-allyloxy coumarin (2 g) and dimethyl aniline (8 ml) was refluxed in an atmosphere of nitrogen for 4 hr. The reaction mixture was worked out as before. The product crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 198°C. Yield 1 g. It gave green colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride. (Found : C, 51.43; H, 3.27; Br, 28.11; calc. for $C_{12}H_9O_3Br$: C, 51.24; H, 3.20; Br, 28.46%).

5-Bromo-2-methyl-9-oxo-9H-2,3-dihydrofuro (2,3-c) *benzopyran* (IIb) : (Ii) (1 g) was triturated with conc. sulphuric acid (5 ml) in a water bath for 15 min. The reaction mixture was poured into crushed ice. The separated product was filtered, washed and dried. It crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 173°C. Yield 0.7 g. It did not develop green colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride. (Found : C, 51.34; H, 3.15; Br, 28.22; calc. for $C_{12}H_9O_3Br$: C, 51.24; H, 3.20; Br, 28.46%).

Attempted dehydrogenation of 5-bromo-2-methyl-9-oxo-9H-2,3-dihydrofuro(2,3-c) *benzopyran* to (IIIc) : (IIb) (0.4 g) was refluxed with diphenyl ether (5 ml)

in the presence of palladised charcoal (0.2 g, 10%) for 6 hr. The reaction mixture was filtered hot and the filtrate on dilution with petroleum ether gave the product which crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 173°C. Mixed m.p. with the original product was not depressed.

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